

Studies on Vanadium Salicyl Hydroxamic Acid Complexes ; A 1:4 Metal-Ligand System

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Vanadium reacts with salicyl hydroxamic acid to form a blue-violet coloured complex with λ_{\max} at 475 nm at pH 3.3. The metal-ligand ratio in the complex is 1:4. The step-wise formation constants of the complexes have been evaluated by Yatsimirskii's and Leden's graphical extrapolation methods from extractive photometric data. The values from $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, $\log K_3$ and $\log K_4$ are 3.65 ± 0.05 , 2.50 ± 0.05 , 2.30 ± 0.05 and 2.15 ± 0.05 respectively.

SALICYL hydroxamic acid has been used for the photometric determination of vanadium¹. Vanadium forms a blue-violet complex extractable in ethyl acetate from a buffer solution of pH 3.3. The complex shows absorption maximum at 475 nm and exhibits a 1 : 4 metal : ligand ratio. The coordination property of this reagent under investigation, appears to be different from other aryl hydroxamic acids which generally form with vanadium a 1 : 3 metal-ligand complex. The present paper deals with the determination of stepwise formation constants of the complexes following extractive spectrophotometric procedure. Both Yatsimirskii's and Leden's graphical extrapolation methods as applied to spectrophotometry were employed for evaluation of the said constants.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions : Ammonium vanadate (A.R.) was used in preparing the standard solution of vanadium. Salicyl hydroxamic acid was prepared and purified by the reported procedure². Solvent, ethyl acetate, and all other chemicals used were A. R. or G. R. quality. Solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Apparatus : Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out on a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. A Beckman Model G pH-meter was used for pH measurements. Evaluation of the said constants was done with CDC 3600 scientific computer. All measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Extraction procedure : An aliquot of vanadium solution ($3.926 \times 10^{-3} M$) is taken in 100 ml separatory funnel and 5 ml of sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer solution of pH 3.3 is added. A desired amount of reagent solution ($3.926 \times 10^{-3} M$) followed by 10 ml of ethyl acetate is added and the contents are shaken for 5 minutes. The organic layer is allowed to settle, then drained out over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The aqueous phase after extraction is treated with 5 ml more of ethyl acetate, shaken and allowed to settle. The organic layer is combined with the previous one,

transferred to a 25 ml flask and diluted with the organic solvent upto the mark. The absorbances are measured at 475 nm against ethyl acetate as blank.

Composition of the complex : Equimolar solutions of vanadium and salicyl hydroxamic acid ($3.926 \times 10^{-3} M$) were utilised to find the metal-ligand ratio by Job's method of continuous variation³ and mole ratio method⁴. Absorbances of three sets of complementary solutions were measured at 475 nm after extracting by the said procedure. The results showed the existence of 1 : 4 complex.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium-salicyl hydroxamic acid complex has λ_{\max} at 475 nm and is of 1 : 4 composition. With a host of other aryl hydroxamic acids vanadium forms complexes with 1 : 3 metal-ligand composition^{5, 6} having absorption maxima range within 540-590 nm with fewer exceptions⁷. Whether these differences in the properties of vanadium-salicyl hydroxamic acid complex from others have any influence on the stability constants of the complex have been investigated.

Formation constants

Yatsimirskii's method : Stepwise formation constants for the 1 : 4 system were found by constructing suitable functions in terms of intercepts obtained at zero-ligand concentration in the manner stated earlier⁶.

The equilibrium ligand concentrations were calculated from Beer's law and based on the assumption that the ligand is tied up with the metal in a ratio of 4 : 1 even at low concentration of the ligand. The functions constructed are :

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} f_1 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\bar{\epsilon}}{[L]} = a_1 \quad (\text{Fig. 1})$$

and

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_{i-1} - a_{i-1}}{[L]} = a_i$$

TABLE 1

Vanadium (V)—Salicylhydroxamic acid complex
 Metal=Reagent= $3.926 \times 10^{-3} M$; Solvent=Ethyl Acetate
 Metal taken=1 ml of $3.926 \times 10^{-3} M$; Final Volume=25 ml.
 Absorbance for total metal conc. $1.5704 \times 10^{-4} M = 0.540$
 $\lambda_{max} = 475 \text{ nm.}$

Total ligand conc. Mole/litre (CL x 10 ⁴)	Absorbance	Equilb. ligand conc. Mole/litre ([L] x 10 ⁴)	Molar absorptivity, (e x 10 ⁻³)	Y (x 10 ⁻³)	f ₁ (x 10 ⁻⁶)	f ₂ (x 10 ⁻¹⁰)	f ₃ (x 10 ⁻¹⁴)	f ₄ (x 10 ⁻¹⁷)	g (x 10 ²)	g ₁ (x 10 ⁻¹)	g ₂ (x 10 ⁻¹²)
6.282	0.420	1.396	2.675	7.163	(-)12.80	2.363	3.483	(-)11.94	(-)10.81	3.736	3.729
7.852	0.425	2.806	2.707	3.563	(-) 9.647	2.300	1.710	(-)12.26	(-)20.84	7.600	7.586
9.420	0.430	4.420	2.739	2.262	(-) 6.197	2.243	1.074	(-) 9.22	(-)31.43	12.12	12.09
10.99	0.440	5.874	2.803	1.702	(-) 4.772	1.930	0.754	(-) 7.485	(-)38.00	16.47	16.44
12.86	0.445	7.684	2.834	1.301	(-) 3.689	1.614	0.535	(-) 6.006	(-)47.34	21.79	21.75
14.13	0.450	8.898	2.866	1.124	(-) 3.224	1.447	0.444	(-) 5.288	(-)51.96	25.52	25.74

where $i = 2, 3, 4$.

The nature of the curve to get values for a_1, a_2 is indicated in Fig. 1. The values for a_3 and a_4 are similarly obtained (figure omitted). The results are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Subsidiary functions f_1 and f_2 as a function of free-ligand concentration L.

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \bar{e} = b_1 = 3.45 \times 10^3 \quad (\text{Fig. 2})$$

$$\text{where } Y = \frac{1}{[L]}$$

and

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} g_n = \frac{\bar{e} - b_{i-1}}{Y} = b_i$$

where $n = 0, 1, 2 ; i = 2, 3, 4$.

Fig. 2 denotes the way the values b_1 and b_2 are evaluated. The values for b_3 and b_4 are obtained in the same way (Figure not included). The results are given in Table 1.

Fig. 2—(a) Mean Molar Extinction coefficient e as a function of the reciprocal of the free-ligand concentration L .
 (b) Subsidiary function g as a function of the reciprocal of the free-ligand concentration L .

The absorptivity, e , values are related to intercept values. After eliminating the e values, four simultaneous equations were obtained which were solved with the help of a computer. The initial guess values required for solving the equations by Fortran programming were supplied by Leden's method of graphical extrapolation. The first iterated values for the formations constants are comparable to those obtained by Leden's method. The log values for K_1, K_2, K_3 and K_4 are 3.65, 2.45, 2.25 and 2.10 respectively.

TABLE 2

Total Ligand conc., Mole/litre (CL × 10 ⁴)	Absorbance	Conc. of Metal complexed Mole/litre (× 10 ⁴)	Equilib. Ligand conc., Mole/litre (× 10 ⁴)	Equilib. Metal conc., Mole/litre (× 10 ⁴)	Conc. of complexing ligand Mole/litre (L × 10 ⁴)	Degree of complex formation function, φ (× 10 ⁻⁸)	Ψ ₁ (× 10 ⁻⁸)	Ψ ₂ (× 10 ⁻⁶)	Ψ ₃ (× 10 ⁻⁹)	Ψ ₄ (× 10 ⁻¹²)
6.282	0.420	1.221	1.396	0.3494	4.884	4.493	7.152	4.202	4.498	7.98
7.852	0.425	1.236	2.806	0.3344	4.944	4.696	7.474	4.746	5.546	11.00
9.420	0.430	1.250	4.420	0.3204	5.000	4.901	7.802	5.282	6.552	11.91
10.99	0.440	1.279	5.874	0.2914	5.116	5.388	8.578	6.719	9.215	16.85
12.86	0.445	1.294	7.684	0.2764	5.176	5.680	9.040	7.612	10.83	19.76
14.13	0.450	1.308	8.898	0.2624	5.232	5.982	9.521	8.447	11.23	20.32

Leden's method: The stepwise formation constants for the 1 : 4 metal-ligand system were evaluated from the following equations:

$$\Psi_1 = \frac{\phi - 1}{L} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 L + \beta_3 L^2 + \dots$$

where the terms have their usual significance⁶. L in this present work denotes the total ligand concentration which being in large excess, is almost equal to free ligand concentration. When L = 0, Ψ₁ reduces to β₁ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3—Subsidiary functions Ψ₁ and Ψ₂ as a function of the total ligand concentration CL.

The function Ψ₂ may be constructed as:

$$\Psi_2 = \frac{\Psi_1 - \beta_1}{L} = \beta_2 + \beta_3 L + \beta_4 L^2 + \dots$$

and it reduces to β₂ when L = 0 (Fig. 3).

Thus the values for β₃ and β₄ are similarly obtained by plotting functions Ψ₃, Ψ₄ against ligand concentrations and extrapolating to zero ligand concentration (Figure omitted). The detailed results are given in Table 2. The values are:

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_1 &= 3.70 & \log K_3 &= 2.35 \\ \log K_2 &= 2.55 & \log K_4 &= 2.20 \end{aligned}$$

The four formation constants values confirm the formation of a 1 : 4 complex. These values obtained by two different methods are in very good agreement. The stepwise stability values are found to be in the decreasing order: K₁ > K₂ > K₃ > K₄. The λ_{max} in this case has been found to be shifted to lower wavelength (475 nm) from the general range of 540 – 590 nm. The overall stability constant is very low (log K = 10.6 ± 0.05). The gradual decrease in the formation constant values and the low magnitude of overall stability constants for a 1 : 4 system point to the possibility of the ligand to act as a unidentate one. However, the stability data alone cannot definitely decide about the nature of bonding and structure of the complex.

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